

SAVOL - JAVOB METODI, BURCHAKLAR METODI, DEBAT (BAHS) METODLARI YORDAMIDA GEOMETRIYANI O'RGANISH.

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Annotatsiya.

Pedagogik texnologiya hozirda barcha pedagogik kasblar hamda talim-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil qilish, boshqarish, nazorat qilish bilan bog'liq kasblarning asosini tashkil qiladi. Maqolada malakaviy ishida innovatsion texnologiyalar va xususiyy innovatsion texnologiyalar haqida to'liq malumot berishga, geometriya dars jarayonida ushbu texnologiyalar asosida o'tishning bazi bir usullari, uning ijobiy natijalarini to'liq yoritib berishga harakat qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: Yo'naltiruvchi, Mozaika, Debat.

Savol - javob metodi:

Savollar 3 xil bo'ladi:

1. Yo'naltiruvchi
2. Ma'lumot beruvchi
3. Esga keltiruvchi

Savol - javob metodidan o'tgan mavzuni so'rash va yangi mavzuni mustahkamlash bosqichida foydalanish yaxshi samara beradi. Savol - javob metodidan foydalangan holda didaktik (ta'limiy) o'yinlardan foydalanilsa ta'limda samaradorlik (o'quvchilar faolligi) oshadi.

Bu o'yinlardan biri - "qo'stingni top" o'yinidir. O'yinni tashkil etish uchun o'tgan mavzuga doir o'quvchilar soniga qarab savol - javob kartochkalari tayyorlanadi. Barcha o'quvchilarga bu kartochkalar tarqatiladi. Shovqin bo'lmasligi uchun bir boshdan savollarni o'qish taklif etiladi. Savolni eshitgan barcha o'quvchilardan birtasiga shu savolning javobi bor u aytishi lozim. Darsda shunday holatlar bo'ladiki hech kimdan sado chiqmaydi unda boshqa savolga o'tiladi. O'yin oxirida kimga javob kartochkasi qolganligi aniqlanadi va bu qaysi savolning javobi ekanligi o'qituvchi va o'quvchilar yordamida topiladi.

Oxirgi so'zni menga qoldiring. Bu metoddan darsda biror muammoni hal qilishda foydalanish mumkin. Barcha o'quvchilar muammoga munosabatlarini bildiradilar. Oxirgi aytgan o'quvchining munosabati qabul qilinadi.

Burchaklar metodi. Burchaklar metodidan foydalanish yo'li quyidagicha: 4 ta burchakka mavzuga doir 4 ta jihoz qo'yiladi. O'quvchilar raqamlanadi. 1,2,3,4

deb. Guruhlar tashkil etilgandan so'ng 1 guruh 1 deb qabul qilingan burchakka boradi va hokazo 4 guruh deb qabul qilingan burchakka boradi. Burchaklardagi jihozlarni olib ular haqida fikr almashadilar va taqdim qiladilar. Jihozlarga qarab o'zlariga nom tanlaydilar. Dars mavzusiga qarab burchaklarga matematikning rasmi, asbob- anjomlar, matbuot materiallari, kompyuter texnikasini qo'yish mumkin. Yuqorida yozilganimizdek guruhlarga ajratgandan so'ng o'quvchilar burchaklarga borib qo'yilgan muammoni hal qiladilar. Bunga 5-10 daqiqa vaqt beriladi. Vaqt o'tgandan so'ng taqdimot o'tkaziladi. Kompyuter texnikasi oldiga borgan o'quvchilar shu mavzuning elektron versiyasini o'rganib o'quvchilarga taqdim qilishlari lozim.

Mozaika metodi. Mozaika so'zining ma'nosi bo'laklardan yig'ib butun hosil qilishdir. Bu usuldan foydalanish uchun oldindan kartochkalarga so'zlar yozilishi kerak. O'quvchi so'zlar ketma - ketligini topib qo'yib gap yasashi lozim. Matematikadagi qonun, qoidalarning so'zlarini alohida kartochkalarda yozish mumkin. har bir qoida, qonun so'zlari yozilgan kartochkalar alohida konvertda saqlanishi lozim. Rasmlarni ham qirqib bo'laklab qo'yilsa o'quvchi yig'ib rasm haqida gapiradi. Guruhlarni ham mozaika metodidan foydalanib tashkil etish mumkin.

Boshqotirma. Bu keng tarqalgan metod hisoblanadi. Aslini olsak bu ham savol-javob metodi, lekin bunda savol og'zaki berilsa javob yozma doska yoki daftariga yoziladi. So'zlar kichkina-kichkina chizilgan to'rtburchaklarda yoziladi. Boshqotirmadan o'tgan mavzuni so'rashda, yangi mavzuning "mavzusini" keltirib chiqarishda, darsni mustahkamlash maqsadida keng foydalanish mumkin.

Mustaqil ish metodi. Bu metoddan darslarda juda ham keng foydalaniladi. O'quvchining masala yechishi, laboratoriya ishini bajarishi, esse yozish, o'z taxminlarini, bilganlarini yozishi va hokazolar o'quvchining mustaqil ishi faoliyatidir.

Debat (Bahs) metodi. Debat (Bahs) o'tkazish uchun o'rtaga biror muammo tanlanadi. Muammoga qarab o'quvchilar 3 guruhga ajraladilar. (ha, yo'q, betaraf). Muammoga "ha" munosabatda bo'lganlar 1 guruh "Yo'q" munosabatda bo'lganlar 2 chi guruh, "betaraflar" 3-guruh bo'ladilar. Navbat bilan o'z nuqtai nazarini aytib o'zini himoya qilishga 1 daqiqadan vaqt beriladi.

Betaraflar ikkala guruh o'quvchilarning fikrlarini tinglab o'z ixtiyorlari bilan "ha" yoki "yo'q" deganlar guruhlarga qo'shiladilar. Himoya davomida "ha" guruhidan "Yo'q" guruhiga o'quvchilar o'tishlari mumkin va aksincha. Debat 7-10 daqiqa davom etishi mumkin (fikrlar bo'lsa yana vaqt berish mumkin).

Esse metodi: Esse bu o'quvchining yozma bayonidir. Esse usulidan yangi mavzuni o'rganish darsida umumlashtiruvchi takrorlash darsida ham foydalanish mumkin. O'quvchilarda darsning mustahkamlash bosqichida yangi olgan ma'lumotlari haqida erkin fikrini yozma bayon qilish topshiriladi. Yozishga 5-7 daqiqa vaqt beriladi. Esselarini taqdim qilishga ham vaqt beriladi.

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